

PREPARATION OF ELECTROSPUN PAN/CNT COMPOSITE FIBRES

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SUMMARY

Electrospinning is a method that can be used to prepare polymeric or composite fibres having diameters typically in a sub-micron range. In this work carbon nanotubes are introduced into solution of polyacrylonitrile for electrospinning. Properties of composite fibres are studied and possible applications of such composite fibres are discussed.

Keywords: electrospinning, composite fibres, CNT, polyacrylonitrile

INTRODUCTION

Sub-micron or nanofibres can be prepared from polymer solution utilizing electrospinning. In electrospinning electrostatic field stretches the polymer solution into fibres at the same time when the solvent is evaporating. Diameters of formed fibres are typically sub-micron range and they can be collected as interconnected nanofiber web onto surface of substrate. [1-3]

Properties of electrospun fibres can be modified using nanosized fillers. Electrospun composite fibres have applications in many areas for example reinforcement, filtration, sensors, fuel cells and nanoelectronics. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are widely used as filler in electrospun fibres [4-12]. Their typical function is serving as reinforcement component [4-6] in electrospun polymeric fibres, but they are also used in order to modify electrical properties of fibres [7-9]. Sen *et al.* [13] have reported a significant increase of 46 % in the tensile strength of PU nanofibres when incorporating single walled nanotubes (SWNT) into a polymer matrix. The mechanical properties depend on the type of SWNT, and chemical functionalization of SWNT's gave rise to even higher tensile strength. Seoul *et al.* [7], on the other hand, report that semiconducting electrospun fibres can be produced with a low CNT loading. The percolation threshold of SWNT was 0.008 wt% in spinning solution or 0.04 wt% in fibre mat [7].

Incorporation of CNTs in polymers enhances the many properties such as tensile strength, modulus and chemical resistance, and it also reduced thermal shrinkage. Reinforcement is one logical application for mechanically strong electrospun composite fibres [14, 15]. Other possible applications field for conductive CNT composite fibres are, for example, nanoelectronics [16], sensors [17, 18] and tissue engineering [19, 20]. Polymeric nanofibres made of certain polymers such as polyacrylonitrile (PAN) can be

used as precursor for fabrication of carbon nanofibres (CNFs) [5, 12, 21-24]. Use of CNT as additive in such precursor fibres may also have some benefits. High concentration of CNTs can resist heat shrinkage of composite fibres during carbonization processes [12]. Presence of CNTs may also enhance growth of carbon crystals during PAN carbonization [23]. Carbonized composite fibres can be used, for example, supercapacitors [25]

Challenge is to disperse the nanofiller uniformly in polymer matrix since presence of agglomerates reduces the bonding area between fillers and matrix [6] and without dispersion percolation threshold is not obtained. Too big agglomerates can also disturb the electrospinning process [26]. In optimal case CNTs are well dispersed and embedded into polymer matrix and possibly also aligned to fibre direction [7].

In this study multi-walled CNTs are included into PAN / dimethylformamide (DMF) solution. Composite solution is electrospun in order to form nanofibre web. Since addition of CNTs into polymer solutions affects the viscosity of the solution, three solutions were prepared: 1) reference solution of neat PAN solution; 2) PAN/CNT solution having same polymer concentration than reference solution; and 3) diluted PAN/CNT solution having same viscosity than reference solution. Suitability of composite solution to electrospinning process is evaluated, and properties of composite fibres are studied and compared with neat polymeric fibres.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Spinning solution of pure PAN was prepared by dissolving polymer (13 wt%) in heated DMF. The solutions were heated and stirred until the polymer was dissolved. Dispersing of CNTs evenly into pure DMF or into viscous polymer solution is difficult, and therefore composite solution was prepared in three steps. First small amount of PAN was dissolved into DMF since it acts as dispersing agent [27]. Then CNTs (0.25 wt%) were added and dispersed into dilute polymer solution with ultrasonic homogenizer. And finally, the rest of the polymer was added in order to obtain preferred polymer concentration (13 wt%). Composite solution was electrospun as such and also diluted to form the third solution. The diluted composite solution had same polymer/CNT ratio than original solution, and thus same CNT content was obtained in fibres.

Electrospinning Experiments

Electrospinning was carried out using continuous equipment in which a horizontal electric field was generated between a nozzle system and a collector plate, and a web having a width of 300 mm was conveyed past the front side of the collector. The nozzle system of the equipment consisted of tubes having ten nozzles each. Inside the tube there was a metallic rod, which was connected to the voltage source (Simco Chagemaster BP 50) from one end of the tube. Solution was fed from the other end of the tube, and nitrogen gas with controlled pressure was attached to the feeding system of the tubes. The collector plate was connected to ground.

Substrates were attached onto nonwoven web. Samples were prepared by conveying substrate with a fixed line speed through the electrospinning zone. Voltage of the solution was set to 28 kV and distance 150 mm. Nozzle sizes of 0.4 mm and 0.5 mm were used depending on the viscosity of the solution. Solution consumption (ml/hour),

which is comparable with productivity, was determined for each solution. Desired basis weight of around 5 g/m^2 was obtained by adjusting the line speed, number of tubes, and amount of process cycles. Paper was used as a substrate.

Electrospun fibre webs were detached from the paper and heat treated by ironing them (low setting around 100°C) between two Teflon coated fabrics in order to compact the nanofiber structure and make its handling easier.

Characterization

Viscosity of the solutions was measured with Brookfield DV-II+ viscometer. SEM imaging of fibres and determination of fibre diameters was conducted using Zeiss Ultra Plus SEM equipment. Image Tool 3.0 software was used for diameter measurements from SEM images. At least 50 measurements from each trial were conducted, and the mean diameter (nm) and its standard deviation (nm) were calculated. The strength of the nanofibre web was studied in tensile test (Testometric M500).

RESULTS

The viscosity of pure 13 wt% PAN solution was around 1150 cP and 13 wt% PAN/0.25 wt% CNT solution 4650 cP. The polymer and CNT concentrations of the diluted composite solution having viscosity of around 1150 cP were around 10 wt% and 0.2 wt%, respectively. Solutions having viscosity of 1150 cP were electrospun using nozzle size of 0.4 mm, but the highly viscous composite solution required larger nozzles of 0.5 mm in order to obtain similar productivity (around 0.4 ml/hour/nozzle).

Color of pure PAN web was white while composite solutions yielded gray web due to the presence of CNTs. All webs had fibrous structure, so the ironing did not affect the fibrous structure. Pure PAN solution and diluted PAN(10%)/CNT solution produced fibres having similar fibre diameters, 270 nm and 240 nm respectively, while the more viscous composite solution PAN(13%)/CNT produced clearly thicker fibres (550 nm), see Figure 1. The fibre diameter was, thus, depended mainly on viscosity of the solution. Fibre diameter distributions of composite fibres were larger than the reference PAN fibres.

Figure 1 Fibre diameters of PAN and PAN/CNT composite fibres. Solution compositions and viscosities are indicated below x-axis.

The appearances of fibres are presented in Figure 2. Surface of the PAN fibres is smooth while composite fibres have surface roughness in form of grooves as well as small bulges (less than 100 nm) that most likely are ends of the CNTs sticking out of the fibre surface. Variation of fibre diameters between fibres and within one fibre is more pronounced in composite fibre samples.

Figure 2 SEM images of PAN fibres (a and b), and PAN/CNT composite fibres made from highly viscous solution (c and d) and diluted solution (e and f). Magnifications used in SEM imaging were 10000x and 20000x.

Stress-strain curves are presented in Figure 3. Tensile test showed that CNTs reduce the straining capacity of nanofibre web. The composite web PAN(13%)/CNT was slightly damaged due to solution droplets during electrospinning, and was clearly weaker than other webs. The effect of CNT can be seen by comparing PAN fibre web and PAN(10%)/CNT composite webs having similar fibre diameters. Their maximum forces were on the same range, around 1 N, but the Young's modulus of PAN web (140 N/mm^2) was only a half of modulus of composite web (280 N/mm^2).

Figure 3 Examples of stress-strain curves of PAN and PAN/CNT composite fibre webs.

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References

1. Li D., Xia Y., Electrospinning of nanofibers: Reinventing the wheel?, *Advanced Materials* 16(14)2004, 1151-1169
2. Ramakrishna S., Fujihara K., Teo W.E., Yong T., Ma Z., Ramaseshan R., Electrospun nanofibers: Solving global issues, *Materials Today (Oxford, United Kingdom)* 9(3)2006, 40-50
3. Greiner A., Wendorff J.H., Electrospinning: A fascinating method for the preparation of ultrathin fibers, *Angewandte Chemie, International Edition* 46(30)2007, 5670-5703
4. Ye H., Lam H., Titchenal N., Gogotsi Y., Ko F., Reinforcement and rupture behavior of carbon nanotubes-polymer nanofibers, *Applied Physics Letters* 85(10)2004, ID 1775
5. Wan Y.Q., He J.H., Yu J.Y., Carbon nanotube-reinforced polyacrylonitrile nanofibers by vibration-electrospinning, *Polymer International* 56(11)2007, 1367-1370
6. Pan C., Ge L.Q., Gu Z.Z., Fabrication of multi-walled carbon nanotube reinforced polyelectrolyte hollow nanofibers by electrospinning, *Composites Science and Technology* 67(15-16)2007, 3271-3277
7. Seoul C., Kim Y.T., Baek C.K., Electrospinning of poly(vinylidene fluoride)/dimethylformamide solutions with carbon nanotubes, *Journal of Polymer Science Part B: Polymer Physics* 41(13)2003, 1572-1577
8. Jeong J.S., Jeon S.Y., Lee T.Y., Park J.H., Shin J.H., Alegaonkar P.S., Berdinsky A.S., Yoo J.B., Fabrication of MWNTs/nylon conductive composite nanofibers by electrospinning, *Diamond and Related Materials* 15(11-12)2006, 1839-1843

9. Park S.H., Jo S.M., Kim D.Y., Lee W.S., Kim B.C., Effects of iron catalyst on the formation of crystalline domain during carbonization of electrospun acrylic nanofiber, *Synthetic Metals* 150(3)2005, 265-270
10. Dror Y., Salalha W., Khalfin R.L., Cohen Y., Yarin A.L., Zussman E., Carbon nanotubes embedded in oriented polymer nanofibers by electrospinning, *Langmuir* 19(17)2003, 7012-7020
11. Yeo L.Y., Friend J.R., Electrospinning carbon nanotube polymer composite nanofibers, *Journal of Experimental Nanoscience* 1(2)2006, 177-109
12. Hou H., Ge J.J., Zeng J., Li Q., Reneker D.H., Greiner A., Cheng S.Z.D., Electrospun polyacrylonitrile nanofibers containing a high concentration of well-aligned multiwall carbon nanotubes, *Chemistry of Materials* 17(5)2005, 967-973
13. Sen R., Zhao B., Perea D., Itkis M.E., Hu H., Love J., Bekyarova E., Haddon R.C., Preparation of single-walled carbon nanotube reinforced polystyrene and polyurethane nanofibers and membranes by electrospinning, *NanoLetters* 4(3)2004, 459-464
14. Foedinger R., Chung S., Ko F., Titchenal N., Roberts J.K., Carbon nanotube reinforced fibers for high strength composite missile cases, *SAMPE Conference Proceedings* 51 2006, 300/1-300/13.
15. Ji J., Sui G., Yu Y., Liu Y., Lin Y., Du Z., Ryu S., Yang X., Significant improvement of mechanical properties observed in highly aligned carbon - nanotube-reinforced nanofibers, *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 113(12)2009, 4779-4785.
16. Sundaray B., Subramanian V., Natarajan T.S., Krishnamurthy K., Electrical conductivity of a single electrospun fiber of poly(methyl methacrylate) and multiwalled carbon nanotube nanocomposite, *Applied Physics Letters* 88(14)2006, 143114/1-143114/3
17. Lala N.L., Thavasi V., Ramakrishna S., Preparation of surface adsorbed and impregnated multi-walled carbon nanotube /nylon-6 nanofiber composites and investigation of their gas sensing ability, *Sensors* 9(1)2009, 86-101
18. Laxminarayana K., Jalili N., Novel carbon nanotube-based fabric sensors: pathway to electronic-textile, 13th National Textile Center Forum [and] 84th Textile Institute Annual World Conference, Raleigh, NC, United States, Mar. 20-25, 2005
19. Han Z., Kong H., Meng J., Wang C., Xie S., Xu H., Electrospun aligned nanofibrous scaffold of carbon nanotubes -polyurethane composite for endothelial cells, *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology* 9(2)2009, 1400-1402
20. Edwards S.L., Church J.S., Werkmeister J.A., Ramshaw J.A.M., Tubular micro-scale multiwalled carbon nanotube -based scaffolds for tissue engineering, *Biomaterials* 30(9)2009, 1725-1731
21. Gu S.Y., Ren J., Wu Q.L., Preparation and structures of electrospun PAN nanofibers as a precursor of carbon nanofibers, *Synthetic Metals* 155(1)2005, 157-161
22. Sutasinpromprae J., Jitjaicham S., Nithitanakul M., Meechaisue C., Supaphol P., Preparation and characterization of ultrafine electrospun polyacrylonitrile fibers and their subsequent pyrolysis to carbon fibers, *Polymer International* 55(8)2006, 825-833

23. Prilutsky S., Zussman E., Cohen Y., The effect of embedded carbon nanotubes on the morphological evolution during the carbonization of poly(acrylonitrile) nanofibers, *Nanotechnology* 19(16)2008, 165603/1-165603/9
24. Saiyasombat C., Maensiri S., Fabrication, morphology, and structure of electrospun PAN-based carbon nanofibers, *Journal of Polymer Engineering* 28(1-2)2008, 5-18
25. Li X., Yu L., Fu H., Chen J., Guo Q., Huang C., Hou H., Electrospun CNTs-embedding carbon nanofibers for supercapacitor, Abstracts of Papers, 237th ACS National Meeting, Salt Lake City, UT, United States, March 22-26 2009
26. Heikkilä P, Nanostructured fibre composites and materials for air filtration, Doctoral Dissertation, Tampere University of Technology. Publication 749. 2008, 91 p.
27. Heikkilä P., Harlin A., Electrospun nanofibres containing carbon nanotubes, 8th Annual World Textile Conference - Autex 2008, Biella, Italy, June 24-26 2008